

BISMUTH-BASED THERMOELECTRIC NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Bulk bismuth-silica nanocomposites have been prepared via powder metallurgy to study the influence of silica inclusions on the transport properties of Bi-based materials. Bi-SiO₂ ultrafine powders were produced by an arc-plasma processing. TEM investigations revealed the presence of a nanometric silica shell around each Bi grain. The nanocomposite powders were cold pressed and sintered close to the melting temperature of bismuth. The electrical resistivity, the thermoelectric power, the thermal conductivity and the thermoelectric figure of merit were measured from 65 K to 300 K. The transport properties of pure single crystalline and polycrystalline bismuth are compared to those of nanocomposite materials.

KEYWORDS: Nanocomposites, bismuth, silica, thermoelectricity, transport properties.

INTRODUCTION

Bi-based semi-conducting alloys are well known for their good thermoelectric properties. Bismuth telluride (Bi₂Te₃) is efficient at room temperature and commonly used for Peltier refrigeration, but its efficiency dramatically decreases at low temperature. Nowadays, Bi-Sb alloys are the best thermoelectric materials below 200 K. The potential of Bi-Sb single crystals for refrigeration near nitrogen liquid temperature has been largely considered during the past decades [1]. However, the use of these single crystals in thermoelectric devices is still difficult because of their poor mechanical properties. In order to improve the durability of the material, polycrystalline alloys have been prepared via powder metallurgy in the last years.

The influence of the microstructure on the thermoelectric properties was studied [2-4]. The thermoelectric figure of merit depends on the thermoelectric power α , the electrical resistivity ρ , and the thermal conductivity λ as follows:

$$Z = \frac{\alpha^2}{\rho\lambda} \quad (1)$$

The grain boundaries were found to reduce the thermal conductivity but it also gave rise to a sharp concurrent increase of the electrical resistivity. As a result, the figure of merit was lower for polycrystalline alloys than for single crystals.

Nevertheless theoretical works have predicted that the efficiency of thermoelectric materials could be significantly enhanced by decreasing the thermal conductivity without affecting the resistivity by a dispersion of nanometric grains of an insulating phase in a large grained matrix [5, 6]. These effects were successfully observed on SiGe-based thermoelectric materials [7].

To study the influence of nanodispersions on the transport properties of bismuth based materials, we prepared Bi-SiO₂ nanocomposites. This paper presents some results on the influence of a silica dispersion on the transport properties of polycrystalline bismuth.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preparation of the powders

Bi-SiO₂ nanocomposite powders containing from 1 to 15 vol. % SiO₂ were prepared by an arc-plasma processing. The technique used was already described in a previous paper [8]. Bi pieces were coevaporated with silica targets under pure argon atmosphere in a DC arc flame. The powders were collected in a glove box under purified argon atmosphere.

The heat transfer between the arc flame and the silica target is the determining factor, which influences both the powder yield and the powder composition. Consequently, the silica content of the powder can be easily controlled by the arc power and depends also on the layout of the raw materials in the arc furnace. Fig. 1 shows the influence of the arc power on the silica content for a given arrangement of the arc furnace.

Fig. 1: Influence of the arc power of the silica content in Bi-SiO₂ powders.

Fig. 2: TEM micrograph of a Bi - 8 vol. % SiO₂ powder.

SEM observations of the powders showed a bimodal distribution of the grain size. The first peak is centred on 1 μm and the second on 0.3 μm . The grains present a spherical shape. Because of the size of the largest grains, TEM observations were carried out on thin sections prepared by ultramicrotomy. Each Bi grain is systematically surrounded by a shell of 2 nm to 10 nm of thickness. This layer can completely encapsulate the Bi grains. EDS and EELS analyses showed this shell was composed of silica. The presence of nanometric silica inclusions was also detected inside the core of the bismuth grains. Nevertheless the observation of these oxide inclusions on TEM bright field micrograph is difficult because of the high atomic number of bismuth and because ultramicrotomy introduces a lot of defaults in the Bi grains. Fig. 2 presents a high resolution micrograph for a Bi - 8 vol. % SiO_2 powder. The shell appears to be nanocrystallised. The silicon oxide phase was identified as tridymite.

Cold pressing

Pellets of 13 mm diameter and 3 mm high were prepared by cold pressing the nanocomposite powders in a stainless steel die under vacuum. This compacting stage was done with fresh powders, in the glove box where the powders are collected. The density of the pellets were evaluated by mass and size measurements and by Archimedes method for the best densified pellets (> 90 %).

Fig. 3 shows the influence of the silica content on the densification rate for two different compacting stresses. For high compacting stress, the densification rate doesn't depend on the powder composition. A densification level higher than 95 % is reached. Whereas, for low compacting pressure, silica has a great influence on the powder compacting. The densification rate increases from 75 %, for pure Bi, to more than 85 %, for a Bi - 15 vol. % SiO_2 powder. This observation can be explained by examining the microstructure of the greens.

Fig. 3: Influence of the silica content on the cold pressing of the Bi - SiO_2 powders.

For a pressure of 600 MPa, the grains lose their spherical shape whatever the silica content is. They are flattened in the direction perpendicular to the axis of pressing (Fig. 4c). On the opposite, for a compacting pressure of 100 MPa (Fig. 4b), any plastic deformation is observable, the grains remain spherical as before compacting (Fig. 4a). It can be concluded that the rearrangement of the grains plays the most important role at low pressure in the cold pressing densification. The silicon oxide surrounding the bismuth favours the rearrangement of the grains by diminishing the friction and by preventing the plastic deformation at low pressure.

Sintering

The carriers and the phonons are highly scattered by the grain boundaries. These scattering

effects have to be diminished as much as possible. It has been shown for Bi-based alloys [2] that the effect of grain boundaries becomes negligible for a grain size of a few hundred microns. In order to study the influence of silica inclusions on the transport properties, polycrystalline materials with the largest grains as possible must be prepared.

Fig. 4: SEM micrographs of a powder. (a) before compacting, (b) 100 MPa cold pressed, (c) 600 MPa cold pressed.

Fig. 5: Fracture surface of Bi pellets showing the microstructure of compacts after annealing during 24h at 260 °C (a), at 267 °C (b).

The greens are annealed under vacuum very close to the melting temperature of bismuth ($T_{fBi} = 271\text{ °C}$) to favour the growth of the matrix grains. The influence of the annealing temperature on the crystalline coalescence and the densification was first studied on Bi samples. Fig. 5 presents the influence of the temperature of the heat treatment on the microstructure. It can be noticed this temperature has to be carefully controlled because of the presence of very small Bi grains ($d < 100\text{ nm}$) which can have a melting temperature lower than that of bulk bismuth [9]. If the melting of the smallest grains of bismuth is favourable to the grain growth, this can induce a partial segregation of the silica grains which is not desirable.

Silica inhibits the grain growth as it prevents the diffusion. As a result, the annealing of composites has to be adapted in order to obtain a grain size comparable to that of pure Bi. Fig. 6 presents the microstructures obtained for a Bi and a Bi - 15 vol. % SiO_2 sample both 600 MPa cold pressed.

Fig. 6: SEM micrographs of pure bulk Bi (a), Bi - 15 vol. % SiO_2 sintered nanocomposite (b).

The average grain sizes are in the same order of magnitude but the shape of the grains are different. In the pure Bi sample, the grains are equiaxed. The flattening of the grains that was induced during pressing is relaxed (Fig. 4c). Whereas for the composite, the grains remain relatively spherical. The two materials have the same relative density. Nevertheless the pore size and their localisation are quite different. Pure Bi presents a few inter granular large pores and small ones which are dispersed in the grains. For the composite material, porosity is only situated at the grain boundaries.

Transport properties

Transport properties measurements were performed on polycrystalline Bi and Bi - SiO₂ samples. Small parallelepipeds (2 x 2 x 10 mm³) were cut with a wire saw from the sintered pellets. The experimental set up has been previously described [3]. A four probe method is used to measure the electrical resistivity. The thermal conductivity and the thermopower were measured by means of a four probe steady heater and sink method.

To evaluate the effect of the grain boundaries, the values are compared to the mean values of a pure bismuth single crystal [10].

The values of the resistivity of the Bi polycrystalline sample are higher than those of single crystal all over the temperature range (Fig. 7a). Contrary to Bi single crystal which is semi-metallic, the polycrystalline Bi sample exhibits a semiconducting behaviour in the 65 K-150 K range. This semiconducting behaviour has been already observed for fine grained Bi polycrystalline samples [11, 12]. It can be explained by considering the scattering of the carriers by the grain boundaries. This scattering is efficient as long as the mean free path of the charge carriers is greater than the grain size. At low temperature, the mean free path in Bi is known to be about a few micrometers [11, 13] which is typically the grain size of our sample. The carriers are consequently subjected to grain boundary scattering. When the temperature increases, the mean free path of carriers decreases and the carriers are less and less scattered by the grain boundaries. As a result, the electrical resistivity decreases. At temperature higher than 150 K, grain boundary scattering is no more efficient and the Bi sample exhibits a classical semi-metallic behaviour.

Fig. 7: Comparison of the transport properties between single and polycrystalline bismuth and Bi - SiO₂ nanocomposites. (a) electrical resistivity, (b) thermoelectric power.

Silica inclusions have a drastic effect on the electrical resistivity. A strong increase of the resistivity is observed for the nanocomposite samples (Fig. 7a). It is attributed to the presence of potential barriers created by the grain boundaries and to the silica inclusions that affect the mobility of carriers. As the composites and the pure Bi polycrystalline have a comparable grain size, it can be assumed that the grain boundary scattering is of the same order of magnitude for the two materials. The very large increase of the resistivity should then be due to a scattering of carriers by the silica inclusions. This scattering effect decreases with the

temperature inducing a decrease of the resistivity with temperature. As a result, the bismuth-silica nanocomposites exhibit a semiconducting behaviour in the whole 80 K - 300 K temperature range. At high temperature, the resistivity of the nanocomposite approaches the value of polycrystalline bismuth.

The thermoelectric power (TEP) of the Bi polycrystalline sample increases in the whole temperature range 65 K - 300 K (Fig. 7b). It is quite constant (between -70 and $-75 \mu\text{V/K}$) from 150 K to 300 K in good agreement with literature data [12, 13]. In this last temperature range, it is higher than that of the single crystal.

The level of the TEP of the nanocomposite materials is unchanged at low temperature compared to polycrystalline bismuth (Fig. 7b). At temperature higher than 150 K, it seems to be slightly enhanced. This behaviour was already seen by other authors on fine grained polycrystalline bismuth and was explained by a size effect [12, 13].

The thermal conductivity of the Bi polycrystalline sample is reduced compared to that of single crystal in the whole temperature range 80 K - 300 K (Fig. 8a). At low temperature, this effect can be attributed to low frequency phonon scattering by the grain boundaries [14]. At high temperature, the grain boundaries effect on phonon scattering is low. Charge carriers are responsible to most of the heat transport and the level of the thermal conductivity have to be compared to the respective values of the resistivity.

The thermal conductivity is reduced for the nanocomposites (Fig. 8a). The obtained value is nearly the same for the two composites, which means that the silica volume fraction is maybe to high. The reduction, which may be due to phonon scattering by the silica inclusions, is higher at low temperature. At higher temperature, phonon scattering by nano-inclusions is less efficient [15] and the composite's thermal conductivity approaches the bismuth's one. Silica inclusions also enhance the electrical resistivity of polycrystalline Bi. Consequently, the carrier scattering can also has a contribution to the thermal conductivity reduction observed for the nanocomposites.

Fig. 8: Comparison of transport properties between single and polycrystalline bismuth and Bi - SiO₂ nanocomposite. (a) thermal conductivity, (b) figure of merit.

The figure of merit of the Bi sample is lower than that of the single crystal, especially at low temperature because of a too high electrical resistivity (about five times the mean value of the

single crystal) which is not compensated by the decrease of the thermal conductivity (Fig. 8a).

Because of the very high electrical resistivity, the figure of merit of the nanocomposites is lower than that of pure Bi in the whole temperature range 80 K - 300 K. This diminution is more important for the Bi 15 vol.% SiO₂ sample. Indeed the silica volume fraction increase has almost no effect on the thermal conductivity (Fig. 8a), whereas it enhances the resistivity (Fig 7a). We are now preparing bulks containing low volume fractions of silica in order to get a significant decrease of the thermal conductivity without to much enhancing the resistivity. Hot pressing will be also used and we expect to obtain larger grain sizes.

The effect observed for the nanocomposite can be attributed to the presence of silica. Nevertheless, the silica distribution in the bulk has not been yet studied. If the silica is situated at the grain boundaries, it should act as a potential barrier. Whereas if the silica inclusions are distributed in the matrix grains, it should act as scattering centres. TEM investigations on the microstructure of bulk nanocomposite materials are in progress in order to better understand the role played by silica on the transport properties.

CONCLUSION

Bismuth-silica nanocomposites were prepared via powder metallurgy. Bi - SiO₂ ultrafine powders containing from 1 to 15 vol.% SiO₂ were obtained by an arc plasma processing. TEM observations associated to EDS and EELS analyses revealed the presence of a silica shell of 2 to 10 nm thick around each Bi grain. This shell is nanocrystallised and identified as trydimite. The powders were cold pressed and sintered under vacuum close to the melting temperature of bismuth. Bulk materials with relative density larger than 97 % and constituted of grains of a few micrometers were obtained. Transport properties were measured from 65 K to 300 K for a pure polycrystalline material and Bi - SiO₂ composites with a comparable grain size. The thermal conductivities of the nanocomposites, are reduced compared to that of polycrystalline bismuth whereas the thermoelectric power is almost unchanged. The concurrent increase of the resistivity, due to a too much high silica volume fraction, leads to a diminution of the figure of merit. Lower volume fractions of silica should be now considered. The effect of hot pressing on the grain size and its consequence on the resistivity will also be studied.

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REFERENCES

1. G.E. Smith, R. Wolfe, "Thermoelectric Properties of Bismuth-Antimony Alloys", *Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol. 33, 1962, pp. 841-846.
2. X. Devaux, F. Brochin, A. Dauscher, B. Lenoir, R. Martin-Lopez, H. Scherrer, S. Scherrer, "Observation of the Grain Size Influence on the Thermoelectric Properties of Polycrystalline Bismuth-Antimony Alloys", *Proceedings of the Sixteenth International Conference on Thermoelectrics*, Dresden, Germany, August 26-29, 1997, A. Heinrich, Ed., IEEE Service Center, Piscataway, pp. 199-202.

3. R. Martin-Lopez, A. Dauscher, H. Scherrer, J. Hejtmanek, H. Kenzari, B. Lenoir, "Thermoelectric Properties of Mechanically Alloyed Bi-Sb Alloys", *Applied Physics A*, 1999, in press.
4. E.H. Volckmann, H.J. Goldsmid, J. Sharp, "Observation of the Grain Size Influence on the Lattice Thermal Conductivity of Polycrystalline Bismuth-Antimony", *Proceedings of the Fifteenth International Conference on Thermoelectrics*, Pasadena, USA, March 26-29, 1996, T. Caillat, Ed., IEEE Service Center, Piscataway, pp. 22-226.
5. G.A. Slack et M.A. Hussain, "The Maximum Possible Conversion Efficiency of Silicon-Germanium Thermoelectric Generators", *Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol. 70, 1991, pp. 2694-2718.
6. P.G. Klemens, "Thermal Conductivity of n-Type Si-Ge", *Materials Research Society Proceedings*, Vol. 234, 1991, pp. 87-94.
7. N. Scoville, C. Bajgar, J. Rolfe, J.P. Fleurial, J. Vandersande, "Thermal Conductivity Reduction in SiGe Alloys by the Addition of Nanophase Particles", *Nanostructured Materials*, Vol. 5, 1995, pp. 207-223.
8. F. Brochin, X. Devaux, J. Ghanbaja, H. Scherrer, "Study of BiSb-SiO₂ Nanocomposite Powders Produced by an Arc Plasma Processing", *Nanostructured Materials*, 1999, in press.
9. B.M. Patterson, K.M. Unruh, S.I. Shah, "Melting and Freezing Behaviour of Ultrafine Granular Metal Films", *Nanostructured Materials*, Vol. 1, 1992, pp. 65-70.
10. B. Lenoir, "Elaboration d'Alliages Bismuth-Antimoine - Contribution à l'Etude des Propriétés de Transport", French thesis, Institut National Polytechnique de Lorraine, Nancy, May 1994.
11. G.A. Ivanov and A.M. Papov, "The Mean Free Path of Carriers in Bismuth and in Bismuth-Antimony Alloys", *Soviet Physics-Solid State*, Vol.5, No. 5, 1963, pp. 1040-1041.
12. G. Cochrane and W.V. Youdelis, "Transport and Thermoelectric Properties of Bismuth and Bi-12 at. pct Alloy Powder Compacts", *Metallurgical Transactions*, Vol. 3, 1972, pp. 2483-2580.
13. J.P. Issi, "Thermoelectric Power of Polycrystalline Bismuth", Belgian thesis, Université Catholique de Louvain La Neuve, Louvain, December 1965
14. H.J. Goldsmid, H.B. Lyon, E.H. Volckmann, "A Simplified Theory of Phonon Boundary Scattering in Solid Solutions", *Proceedings of the Fourteenth International Conference on Thermoelectrics*, M.V. Vedernikov, Ed., St Petersburg, Russia, June 27-30, 1995, pp. 16-19.
15. J.P. Fleurial, "Evaluation of the Improvement in the Figure of Merit of Bi₂Te₃-Based Alloys with Addition of Ultrafine Scattering Centers", *Proceedings of the Twelfth International Conference on Thermoelectrics*, K. Matsuura, Ed., Yokohama, Japan, November 9-11, 1993, pp. 1-5.